

Religion in Greco-Roman Egypt

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Egyptian Religions, Greek Religions, Hellenistic Religions, Greek Cult

This area of interest deals with the cults and beliefs prominent in Egypt during the Ptolemaic and Roman periods. The cults in this period were radically transformed from their earlier, pharaonic versions, becoming a complicated mix of different traditions. Egyptian beliefs and practices were merged with the Greek cults. New cults emerged alongside those that were transformed, such as the cult of Serapis, the main god of Alexandria. The Egyptian deities interacted with Greek partners and were worshipped side by side in the Egyptian metropolis.

Date Range: 305 BCE - 284 CE

Region: Africa, Egypt

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa

The extent of the Nile valley from the Delta to modern Sudan, sometimes extending into the Levant and Near East. In the Hellenistic period, Egyptian and Egyptian cultic practices began to spread through the Mediterranean, becoming popular in Italy under the Roman Empire

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: H. I. Bell, *Cults and Creeds in Graeco-Roman Egypt*, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, 1954
- Source 2: D. Frankfurter, *Religion in Roman Egypt*, Princeton University Press, New Jersey, 1998
- Source 3: R. Merkelbach, *Isis regina - Zeus Sarapis*, Teubner Stuttgart und Leipzig, 1995

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781444338386.wbeah07098>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 3 Description: papyri and Ostracas

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General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: The Greeks who lived in Egypt during the Ptolemaic and Roman periods were influenced by ancient Egyptian religion. They practiced Egyptian cults and worshiped Egyptian deities. They also joined their Greek deities with the Egyptian local deities in Egypt in a practice referred to as "syncretism". They also created a new god named Serapis who became the supreme god of Egypt during this period.

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Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

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Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

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Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: Although "scriptures" may not be quite the appropriate term, the Egyptians at this time did inscribe sacred writing on the walls of temples, and priests kept sacred texts on papyri as well.

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Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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Are they oral:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– I don't know

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Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

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– Yes

Notes: The religion itself was transformed and complicated during this period - this goes for religious architecture and monuments as well. New Greco-Roman styles of art and decoration were created. In addition, they also established Greco-Egyptian styles of monuments (tombs, temples, shrines). The Great temple of Serapis at Alexandria is a good example. It was created in the Greco-Egyptian style. We can also note that this type of mixed architectural elements frequently appeared in the Egyptian Metropolis where the Greek and Egyptian deities were worshiped side by side in same religious buildings and monuments.

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Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

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↳ Tombs:

– Yes

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↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

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↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

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↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: small religious buildings in domestic contexts, like small shrines in private houses or military camps

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Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

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↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

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Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Ancient Egyptians believed in an after life. They thought that the spirit could return to the body. During the Greco-Roman periods these beliefs and cults influenced by the ancient Egyptian beliefs and people have to participate the same cults in their tombs.

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Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

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Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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Human sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Other grave goods:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

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Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The forms of burials during the Ptolemaic and Roman periods went through significant transformations and changes. The Greek inhabitants who lived in Alexandria and Urban Greek cities in Egypt used to buried themselves in same type of burials and tombs as those found in Greece. During the early Ptolemaic period the Greeks used to burn their bodies, putting bone in Large vessels so-called Hydria vases, which were then buried in main chambers of the tombs, a practice unheard of during the pharaonic period. The tombs included a number of chambers under the ground. Each chamber has holes so-called "Liculus" "Plur. Liculi" which were used to buried the deceased. The Western and eastern necropolis of Alexandria is considered to be a very good example of these types of the early Ptolemaic tombs in Egypt.

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↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The Egyptians in the Greco-Roman period believed in several types of supernatural beings. Many of these were worshipped in order to receive power or fertility. They believed that supernatural beings could control their fate. A good example is the god Tutu whose cult was wide spread in Egypt during the Late Period and Greco Roman periods. Tutu was worshiped as the god of fate who could change a bad fate to a good one if the worshippers supplicated to him.

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↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god of this period is the god Serapis. Serapis is the great deity of Alexandria and the main god of the Ptolemaic kingdom. The cult of Serapis was created during the beginning of the Ptolemaic Period and his cult spread rapidly through the Egyptian and the Hellenistic kingdoms. Serapis incorporated attributes of both Greek and Egyptian deities. He took on aspects of the great Greek god Zeus and the Egyptian Osiris. He also incorporated aspects of Dionysos, Hermes, Herakles, Helios, and the Egyptian Amun Re and Atum. Serapis therefore became a universal god and had the ability to control the fate of humans as the god of the afterlife.

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↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

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↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: not only sky deity but also terrestrial deities could be do the same functions

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↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Appears in a majestic position usually

Specific to this answer:

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↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: According to the ancient beliefs, the supreme gods knew everything about places, dates, and humans who they created.

Specific to this answer:

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↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: the supreme gods and goddess created the Universal regions and they can control the humans and animals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– No
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant
- ↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Alexander the Great for example dream his father's soul who asked him to go to siwa in Egypt to prove this birth from lineage of Amun Re.

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In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Through divination processes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Only through specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: The kings sometimes uses this ideas to prove their legitimacy

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: it could be a figurines or amulets or something like this

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: May be, we can see this in the Egyptian beliefs and cults clearly

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

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Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

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Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

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Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

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Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

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Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

Specific to this answer:

Region: Egypt, sometimes Nubia (Sudan) and the Levant

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